

A Preliminary Study on Diversity of Spiders (Araneae) of Gavier Lake, Surat, Gujarat

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Abstract

This study presents a preliminary investigation into the diversity of spiders (Araneae) within the Gavier Lake ecosystem in Surat, Gujarat. Conducted from September 2022 to March 2023, the research aimed to document spider species richness and examine their ecological roles within this freshwater wetland. Gavier Lake, noted for its rich biodiversity, provides a unique habitat for a wide range of terrestrial and aquatic species. Spiders were sampled using visual search methods across various habitat layers and time periods to capture both diurnal and nocturnal species. The study underscores the role of spiders as bioindicators and key predators in the wetland ecosystem, highlighting the need for further research and conservation efforts to protect Gavier Lake's diverse arthropod fauna.

Keywords: Spider diversity, Araneae, Freshwater wetland, Biodiversity, Terrestrial arthropods

Introduction

Freshwater wetlands are among the planet's most valuable yet threatened ecosystems (Costanza et al., 2014). Invertebrates play a crucial role in sustaining these ecosystems, with terrestrial arthropods being especially important. While research on freshwater wetlands often emphasizes aquatic invertebrates, terrestrial species also make substantial contributions to ecosystem health (Adis & Junk, 2002). Among these,

terrestrial invertebrates are vital components of wetland food webs and serve as bioindicators of ecosystem health (Batzler & Wu, 2020). Generalist predators, such as spiders (Araneae), are abundant in wetlands and play essential roles, particularly in vegetation-rich areas like peatlands (Holmquist et al., 2011; Scott et al., 2006). This study aims to examine the diversity of spiders around Gavier Lake, a freshwater wetland near Surat, Gujarat, India. Known for its rich

biodiversity, Gavier Lake is surrounded by native trees and dense vegetation planted through conservation efforts by Nature Club Surat. This vegetation attracts a variety of invertebrates, providing an ideal microhabitat for spiders and making the lake an excellent site for studying spider diversity. The lake's complex ecosystem supports a range of species, including reptiles, amphibians, birds, and spiders, all contributing to the ecological balance of the wetland. Spiders in this habitat, in particular, depend on the abundance of insects, especially during the monsoon season when insect populations peak.

Methodology

- a. The study was conducted at Gavier Lake from September 2022 to March 2023. To maximize species richness, spiders were surveyed at different times of day, with sampling conducted in the morning (7:00 am - 11:00 am), evening (4:00 pm - 6:00 pm), and night (7:00 pm - 9:00 pm). This approach targeted both diurnal and nocturnal species.

b. Sampling Method:

- i. **Visual Searching:** Spiders were located using visual searches, with a white light torch used for evening and nighttime observations.
- ii. **Ground Layer:** Spiders were actively searched on the ground and low-level habitats such as rocks, grasses, fallen leaves, decaying plant matter, water surfaces, and small plants.
- iii. **Aerial Layer:** Spiders were also searched in habitats up to 1.5 meters above the ground, including tree trunks, branches, webs, leaves, and other elevated areas.

c. Collection Method:

- i. **Glass container:** Jumping spiders and ground spiders were captured using a glass container.
- ii. **Hand-picking:** Web-building spiders, like orb weavers, were collected by hand-picking directly from their webs (Tikader, 1987).

iii.

d. Data Analysis

Data analysis was done to calculate species diversity and evenness indices by the following methods.

3) Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index (Shannon and Wiener, 1949)

$H = -\sum p_i \ln p_i$, Where, H= Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index, p_i = the

relative abundance of each group of organisms.

4) Pielou's Evenness Index (Pielou, 1966)

$J' = H / H_{max}$, Where, J' = Pielou evenness index, H= The observed value of Shannon index, $H_{max} = \ln S$, S= Total number of species

Results

Figure 1. Different families found in Gavier Lake, Surat, Gujarat.

Figure 2. Abundance of spiders based on families

The diversity and abundance of spiders at Gavier Lake indicate that the families Araneidae and Salticidae are dominant, both in terms of species diversity and population abundance. Araneidae accounts for 25.32% of the total spider population, while Salticidae represents 21.64%. Other families, such as Lycosidae and Thomisidae, also demonstrate significant diversity and presence. The Pisauridae family is represented by only one genus and species, *Thalassius albocinctus*, commonly known as the fishing spider. The study results showed a species diversity index of 3.4522 and an evenness index of 0.833.

Discussion

The diversity index and species evenness results indicate a relatively high number of spider species with an even distribution of individuals across these species (Paschetta et al., 2012). These values suggest a well-balanced ecosystem around Gavier Lake, where no single species dominates, contributing to the stability and resilience of the community. Such balance is crucial for ecosystem health, as a diverse and evenly distributed community is better equipped to withstand environmental changes and disturbances. The complex structure of the wetland,

with its variety of microhabitats, provides niches for different spider species, promoting greater diversity. Certain spider families, such as Salticidae and Araneidae, are effective predators that help maintain ecological balance by controlling pest populations (Priyadarshini et al., 2015). The high abundance and diversity of spiders further highlight the health of the wetland ecosystem, as spiders are recognized bioindicators. A balanced community structure suggests a healthy population and overall ecological stability. Additionally, the relationship between high plant diversity and spider richness emphasizes the importance of preserving vegetation complexity in wetland conservation efforts.

Conclusion

This preliminary study of spider diversity at Gavier Lake provides valuable insights into the rich arachnid fauna within this freshwater wetland ecosystem. The variety of spider species documented highlights the ecological importance of the lake's complex habitat structure. Serving as both predators and bioindicators, spiders play a crucial role in supporting

the wetland's health and stability. The findings underscore the need for ongoing monitoring and conservation efforts to preserve Gavier Lake's ecological integrity. Future research should aim to expand the species inventory and investigate the specific ecological roles of different spider guilds to deepen our understanding of their contribution to wetland biodiversity.

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